
The next generation of smartphone travel data collection with implementation of complex stakeholder's support approach

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Abstract - Traditional travel behaviour surveys or data collection are facing to the various problems resulting from difficulties in the process of reaching and recruiting potential participants. Thanks to new generation ICT (information and communication technology) tool as the smartphone, we can investigate more than travel mode or trip purpose. Nowadays the smartphone travel data collections are becoming of central importance in collecting detailed, accurate data of people's travel activities, but moreover also their feedback, quality evaluation in real time environment. To be successful in data collection, there is need for cooperation and stakeholders' engagement during the planning of the data collection. As with their traditional data collection counterparts, the quality of data collected through these surveys is adversely affected by participants' non-response and resulting biases. Therefore, the main aim of this article is present the new travel behaviour survey within MoTiV project with stating the stakeholder role in data collection campaign.

Keywords — *travel behaviour; data collection; value of travel time; transport.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Investigating various aspect of transport leads to the need of data collection related to the personal travel behaviour. These travel surveys have various forms from the simplest face to face interview, or paper diary to computer assisted or phone assisted surveys. Together with smartphone came along the opportunity to use the smartphone for additional task, not only for calling. For instance, the integration of GPS allowed to track and measure the sport performance or use the navigation. Especially for long term period the usage of travel survey can be fruitful in evaluation and systematic approaches of transport planning process and transport policy evaluation. In some countries, (e.g. Germany [24], Netherlands [25]) they are using the panel mobility behaviour surveys to evaluate, analyse and compare the long-term travel behaviour. The need for long-term survey was also proved for instance in Korea in 8-year study comparison [3].

II. EXPERIENCES WITH SMARTPHONE BASED DATA COLLECTIONS

There have been several trials and pilots based on the smartphone data collection. Based on the current state of art, there is a big potential for national surveys [18].

If we compare, for instance how many cities or countries in are regularly conducting such kind of travel behaviour data collection with the same methodology, the evidence [1] shows various approaches. There have been projects that focused on the urban sustainable mobility, for instance project PASTA [29]. But, there are still countries, e.g. Slovak republic, with no systematic approach in travel behaviour data collection. Most of the cities or villages don't know about how their citizen travel, what are their expectations or preferences.

In Europe, there were some trials with smartphone – based data collection, for instance METPEX [26] with surveys in 8 cities, SOMOBIL [7]. Another applications SmartMo was tested only in Austria [8] or MoveSmarter in Netherlands [9]. The ongoing project are for instance, TravelVU [31] or Modalyzer [27] which is not geographically restricted; the participants can be from all around the world.

The non-European trials were conducted for instance in Singapore [11], in Australia and New Zealand [12] with app ATLAS II or in China [13] and Japan [14].

As we can see from the trials, the smartphone-based data collection becomes the innovative and promising approach how to collect data.

The opportunity for each country is offering by innovative research project, called Mobility and Time Value (MoTiV), within the H2020 framework. This project will launch the European wide smartphone data collection, but it can be conducted all around the world [24]. The project aims deals with new definition of Value of Travel Time [19, 21].

A. Parameters to be collected

The smartphone-based data collection has wide range of parameters that can be collected. We can divide them into following:

- Trip purpose,
- Travel mode,
- Trip trajectory and performance data,
- Satisfaction with service,
- Sensor data about smoothness,
- Weather data,
- Safety data.

Some of these parameters is possible to collect automatically (GPS trajectories, data from other sensors), some of them can be recognized semi automatically (it is necessary to define some parameters at the beginning and later based on the machine learning algorithm the smartphone automatically recognize the trip purpose or place), the same is in case of travel mode. The last category are the parameters where is needed the personal input from the users (e. g., quality evaluation, the comments, mood, etc.). This is very important if we are redefining the new approach in the Travel Time issue [22].

III. ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF SMARTPHONE BASED SURVEYS

A. The advantages of the smartphone-based survey

First, the ICT can provide the easy way how to collect data via personalized tool, smartphone, which is still available by person. The study [2] summarized the perception and experience of smartphone-based study in Australia. There can be also collected various parameters via smartphone. The smartphone can have already integrated various sensors which can collect data automatically without any human involvement. But on the other hand, there can be special data that are related to the personal feedback of users, for instance mood, feeling which are related more to the personal subjectivity.

Another advantage is an administration and preparation of such kind of data collection. The traditional surveys require a long-time period for preparation and running. The smartphone-based data collection is much more flexible for updating the questions.

One of the biggest advantages is time of the data collection. For smartphone-based travel survey is not the limit (i. e. sample size, time) for data collection [20]. It is suitable for short-term as well as for long term travel surveys with potentially wide range of parameters to be collected. Therefore, we can consider smartphone-based survey as the next generation of data collections.

High cost of survey [10] can be referred as one of the highest obstacles for countries or cities for conducting the regular surveys in traditional form (e.g. paper) or Computer Assisted Telephone Interview (CATI). This can be overcome

by implementing the data collection based on the information technologies. Wide penetration of smartphones allows to target easily almost in whole population without need to distribute the survey forms and collect them back from users.

B. Disadvantages of the smartphone-based survey

The main problem of smartphone-based data collection consists in fact that even we have a good penetration of smartphone across population, there is still a need to use specific app to start collection of data. Another obstacle of using such kind of application is fact, that it is not popular and used for everyday life, so therefore the promotion is one of the crucial points. The main purpose of this app is mainly for the research, science or specific usage group, so the potential personal engagement is limited even it is public and free to download and use.

The next serious obstacle is represented by availability of smartphone among various groups of populations, what is related mainly to elder people. We can see, that for some groups [5] the smartphone ownership can be problematic based on the expensive price. For instance, comparing the academic to other environment or factors [6]. But based on the all above mentioned disadvantages, we see the smartphone-based data collection promising and therefore we have decided to overcome these negatives with stakeholder's engagement.

IV. PLANNING THE DATA COLLECTION WITH STAKEHOLDERS ENGAGEMENT IN MOTIV PROJECT

Researchers and analysts around the world are facing to the problem of insufficient sample for the data collection. Therefore, this process requires a detailed planning or efficient sampling strategy. The disadvantages of the smartphone-based data collection can cause that the estimated target group will be not reached. For this reason, we have seen the stakeholder's engagement as the one of the main pillars of the successful data collection campaign.

Considering the potential risk, the preparation of the data collection has been divided into two-time phases. The first phase is focused on the planning of the activities including the stakeholders' engagement, promotion channels, outreach events, etc. Second phase is focused on the implementation of the planned activities. This should be planned very carefully with considering the overall goal of data collection campaign.

The overall goal of MoTiV data collection campaign is to gain at least 5 000 users among 10 partners countries. Due to the specific feature of the app which will be probably not so popular [23] as Viber [32] or WhatsUp [33], we need to promote the data collection campaign as much as it is possible. For this task the importance of stakeholder's engagement was envisaged. To attract the stakeholders, we must answer to the following questions:

- Who are our stakeholders?
- How will we engage them?
- What is the role of stakeholders?

- What will be the benefits for them to participate?

A. Stakeholders engagement.

The stakeholder's engagement consists of various steps, starting from their identification followed by contacting and negotiating them for the purposes of data collection campaign. The identification of stakeholders assumes the fact, the data collection will be attractive for them. In the MoTiV project, we count mainly with three types of stakeholders.

1. The official authorities as municipalities, regional government, etc.,
2. Transport and mobility service providers,
3. NGO, citizens groups.

Each of this group can have a different reason for promoting and participating in the data collection campaign. Based on this, each partner has started to engage and recruit the potential stakeholders.

B. Role of stakeholders

The stakeholders can be involved in data collection campaign via the different roles. They can evaluate the credibility [15] of various programs as well as the data collection. Their input could be useful in the policy strategy planning [16] considering also their transdisciplinary. They can even represent the target group of data collection or they can contribute to creation of questions, which will be part of the data collection campaign.

In the case of MoTiV project, we have grouped them into two basic groups. First, the promoter role, which implies the promotion of the campaign. Second, active role in terms of users' recruitment. There can be also mix of these roles.

The active role also means that in the case of lower participation rate, the stakeholder can promote the data collection campaign more.

The best case is if stakeholder is interesting in the topics of data collection and can have the benefit from it. In this case, it is like WIN – WIN model for both, stakeholders and campaign organizers. There are good examples of such kind of cooperation and synergy effect, for example [17].

C. The benefits for stakeholders

- Municipality can benefit from the status analysis knowing more about the travel behaviour and citizens needs within the city.
- Transport and mobility service providers will be more interesting in data reflecting the transport demand, but also the satisfaction with provided quality.
- NGOs can benefit from the data that will support their goals or aims.

The most interesting benefit and output of stakeholder's participation in this data collection campaign is Open Dataset available for general public after data collection ends.

This is also related to the cost of such kind of data collection. The cooperation in the process of data collection can bring the fruitful output for stakeholders without planning or running the survey standalone, which will require additional extra cost from stakeholders.

Additional advantage of cooperation is transdisciplinary approach. The collected data are not focused only on the one single purpose, but they will be supplemented by additional data from multiple areas, bringing a new perspective on the issue to the stakeholder. New context can often be discovered, which have often been neglected, especially because stakeholders did not have available such data.

Of course, there might be also other reasons for entering or participating in data collection by stakeholders, for example prestige, European wide dimension, comparison or benchmarking statistics as well as many other factors from the long-term perspective.

V. PREPARATION OF DATA COLLECTION PLANS

Based on the potential problems that might occur during the data collection campaign, all partners and third linked countries had to prepare the national data collection campaign plans. The baseline request for those plans, was to prepare for a survey in each country with respect to minimize the risk of failure of the data collection.

To engage the country specific stakeholders was one of the important tasks. Each partner led an extensive stakeholder engagement effort consisting of numerous groups across the country to understand the types of data that were important to them, and the type of output they needed.

Every country is planning the campaign by themselves with their selected stakeholders, their promotion channels or outreach events, see Fig.1.

Figure 1. Example of process flow between stakeholders and specific users group.

In summary, we have various approaches in the campaign planning. The national wide approach for countries as

Slovakia, Finland or Italy, which plan to involve the stakeholders from different regions. Switzerland has decided to prepare a plan only with one local stakeholder. The specification of plan should cover the potential users required in the sample from the view of various criterions as we have mentioned before. That means if we need for data collection the specific group of young people, our stakeholders should cover this age group with their promotion channels, own or joint outreach events. The same approach is in the case of population distribution in rural or urban areas. Such approach can reduce the risks related to the sample size.

A. Linkage to sample size

The stakeholders' engagement can help to reach the required sample size especially if there is need for the representative sample including the major age groups, gender, rural and urban population, etc.

That means the diversity of stakeholders can better target these various groups and easier reach them. Based on the age specification the MoTiV DCC is focused on the four main age groups:

- 16-24,
- 25-49,
- 50- 64,
- 65 and more.

The various stakeholders can target on specific groups with relevant promotional channels. Of course, we can have the stakeholders that are focused only on the specific groups. For instance, the regional bus company will be interested in recruiting of their passengers, the same approach can be applied for the railway company. But within this specific group, they will try focus on the various age groups from young to elderly group.

To enhance the chance, attract the specific group with limited IT skills, we are going to organize also special trainings or workshop. This will be possible with help of specific stakeholders that are dealing with such group. For instance, the university of third age will allow to present data collection campaign during their lessons delivered for elderly people.

The young age group targeting will be possible with the cooperation with regional or local authorities that have responsibilities of this group. According the experience of various groups, there will be applied also various promotional channels that can easily target the specific target group.

It is also possible that some groups will be targeted by similar stakeholders, see Fig. 2.

Figure 2. Example of stakeholders targeting on specific groups.

Based on the national statistics we have calculated the required number of potential users for each country. For example, in the case of Slovakia, the table I. shows the required target group. The values have been calculated based on the Slovak statistics data [30].

TABLE I. TARGET SAMPLE BASED ON THE AGE GROUPS FOR SLOVAKIA

AGE GROUP	POPULATION SHARE (IN %)	TARGET SAMPLE (# OF DCC PARTICIPANTS)
16-24	13,57	96
25-49	45,09	318
50-64	23,96	169
65 and more	17,39	125
Minimum Target		700

The similar calculation can be provided when considering the gender (see Table II) as well as the population distribution among the rural and urban areas (see Table III).

TABLE II. TARGET SAMPLE BASED ON THE GENDER FOR SLOVAKIA

GENDER	SHARE (IN %)	TARGET SAMPLE (# OF DCC PARTICIPANTS)
Men	49	349
Women	51	357
Minimum Target	100%	700

TABLE III. TARGET SAMPLE BASED ON THE URBAN AND RURAL AREAS

AREA OF RESIDENCE	SHARE (IN %)	TARGET SAMPLE (# OF DCC PARTICIPANTS)
Urban areas	54	378
Rural areas	46	322
Minimum Target	100%	700

But for example, some countries will focus in their campaigns only on the urban or metropolitan areas, because their stakeholders cannot guarantee to reach potential users in rural areas.

The ideal case is if the stakeholders can cover the majority of target group (e. g. junior or senior only) by recruiting the potential users. Because, the partners approaches are different, some of partners are planning to do only digital campaigns, some of them are preparing the outreach events to recruit users. For instance, in Slovakia, the recruitment process already started 6 months before planned data collection campaign with already 36 % of signed potential users. This will help reduce the risk of insufficient sample.

All consortium (Belgium, Croatia, Finland, France, Italy, Norway, Slovakia, Switzerland, Portugal,) is planning to realize around 50 outreach events with around 100 stakeholders.

Based on this there are prepared the DCC plans with lists of various stakeholders which can cover the potential survey participants with promotional channels or outreach events.

VI. USERS DATA PRIVACY

An important issue is related to the personal privacy. We understand that some data can be sensitive in sense of data privacy. All consortium therefore prepared the data privacy approach where the responsibility for data privacy has been solved with help of the Ethics and Data Protection Managers. The data collection meets the GDPR requirements and each person willing to participate must give a consent. All collected data will be anonymized and no personal data will be published. During the data collection all users can quit the participation and request the deleting of their data.

VII. CONCLUSION

The smartphone-based data collection campaign is becoming more and more popular nowadays. As it was discussed in section three, this kind of travel surveys has its advantages but also disadvantages. Important part of these

surveys is their dissemination via different channels. The purpose of involvement of different stakeholders in data collection campaign is to attract the broad public of respondents who will participate in the data collection. This approach should ensure the smooth process of data collection with enough respondents. The paper presents the approach for international data collection in Europe in MoTiV project. This will allow to compare various parameters among various countries with high impact on research or transport planning. To stress on stakeholder's engagement seems to be crucial point for smartphone-based data collection. This is mainly for reason that the adequate selection of stakeholders should also ensure the coverage of participants in data collection of different age groups as well as distributed proportion from the geographical perspective.

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